

EXPLORERS

Exceed your limits.
Become the BEST.

EMBRY-RIDDLE Aeronautical University

Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University

Department of Electrical, Computer, Software and Systems Engineering

Security and Optimization for Networked Globe Laboratory

daytonabeach.erau.edu

@EmbryRiddle

Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University is the world's largest and most respected university specializing in aviation and aerospace, with over 130,000 graduates around the globe.

The **Department of Electrical, Computer, Software, and Systems Engineering (ECSE)** work on the technologies that make air and space flight possible. From navigation and control systems to the electroluminescent dimming of the windows in a 787 airliner, these technologies involve embedded computers like those found in mobile phone and flight control systems.

The mission of the Security and Optimization for Networked Globe Laboratory ([SONG Lab](#)) to advance research and education through discovery and innovation at the confluence of cybersecurity, privacy, AI/machine learning, communications and networking, and cyber-physical systems (CPS).

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x3 CHALLENGES

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Manufacturing
Health
Transport
Space
Environment
Security

CHALLENGE #2 - ERAU-IOT-01

→ Internet of Dependable and Controllable Things

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Develop enabling technologies towards a vision of an "Internet of Dependable and Controllable Things" while preserving the enormous potential benefits.

OBJECTIVES

IoT devices sense and communicate information, and in some cases act upon that information. Their rapid emergence brings the promise of important new benefits to consumers and opportunity for huge economic growth. However, it also presents important challenges in security, safety, and privacy.

SKILLS REQUIRED

Fundamental concepts of wireless communication; 802.11 standards and protocols; Linux networking concepts; Software-defined networking concepts; Linux kernel development; C/C++, Python.

CHALLENGE #3 - ERAU-LEARN-02

→ Verifiable Reinforcement Learning

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Reinforcement learning and sequential decision-making have been revolutionized in recent years thanks to advancements in deep neural networks. One of the most recent breakthroughs was accomplished by the AlphaGo system and its victory over the world Go champion. However, even in this impressive system, the learned agent performed sub-optimal actions that puzzled both the Go and the reinforcement learning communities. Such failures in decision-making motivate the need for methods that can provide (statistical) guarantees on the actions performed by an agent. We are interested in establishing such guarantees in both discrete and continuous systems where agents learn policies, or action plans, through experience by interacting with their environment.

OBJECTIVES

Some problems of interest in this domain include, but are not limited to the following:

- Decision-making in partially observable Markov Decision Processes.
- Satisfying probabilistic guarantees on the behavior of a learned agent when approximate value functions (i.e. neural networks) are used to measure utility.
- Control of hybrid systems resulting from the discretization of continuous space induced by a given set of behavioral specifications. Such specifications are typically defined by a temporal logic such as computation tree logic and l
- inear temporal logic.
- Decision-making in adversarial stochastic games.
- Reinforcement learning as a constrained optimization problem wherein expected long-term rewards are to be maximized while satisfying bounds on the probabilities of satisfying various behavioral specifications.

SKILLS REQUIRED

A basic understanding of Reinforcement Learning.

CHALLENGE #4 - ERAU-DATA-03

→ Data-Efficient Machine Learning

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

This topic focuses on the investigation and development of data-efficient machine learning methods that are able to leverage knowledge from external/existing data sources, exploit the structure of unsupervised data, and combine the tasks of efficiently obtaining labels and training a supervised model. Areas of interest include, but are not limited to: Active learning, Semi-supervised learning, Learning from "weak" labels/supervision, One/Zero-shot learning, Transfer learning/domain adaptation, Generative (Adversarial) Models, as well as methods that exploit structural or domain knowledge. Furthermore, while fundamental machine learning work is of interest, so are principled data-efficient applications in, but not limited to: Computer vision (image/video categorization, object detection, visual question answering, etc.), Social and computational networks and time-series analysis, and Recommender systems.

OBJECTIVES

Many recent efforts in machine learning have focused on learning from massive amounts of data resulting in large advancements in machine learning capabilities and applications. However, many domains lack access to the large, high-quality, supervised data that is required and therefore are unable to fully take advantage of these data-intensive learning techniques. This necessitates new data-efficient learning techniques that can learn in complex domains without the need for large quantities of supervised data.

SKILLS REQUIRED

A basic understanding of Machine Learning.

